

Orthophosphate of Thorium

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Thorium phosphate tetrahydrate is reported^{1,2,4,5} to be formed as a white gelatinous precipitate by the interaction of solutions of a thorium salt and an alkali phosphate. The existence of the tetrahydrate has, however, been doubted⁶. The normal orthophosphate, as prepared by Castel³ on dehydration at 105°, afforded a product containing 16.5% water, corresponding to a 12-hydrate.

In the present attempts to prepare the tetrahydrate, the influence of pH and precipitation temperature has also been studied. It has been found that the best conditions for obtaining an easily filtrable precipitate are to precipitate from a hot thorium nitrate solution containing an electrolyte (8% w/v ammonium nitrate) at pH 2.0 and boiling the solution after addition of H₃PO₄ for a minute. In all cases, the precipitate contained water corresponding to 85-135 moles and in no case was the tetrahydrate obtained directly or even on long boiling for 6 to 8 hr. A D.T.A. and T.G.A. study was undertaken to ascertain if the tetrahydrate could be obtained as a stable phase at some elevated temperature. Bulk quantity of the orthophosphate was prepared and dried in an oven at 110° for 16 hr. The period for which Castel³ dehydrated the sample at 105° is not known. Several samples prepared were chemically analysed by standard methods (Table I)

TABLE I

No.	Water.	% Th.	% P.	ThO ₂ /P ₂ O ₅ .	
				Obs.	Calc.
1	60.00	25.88	4.59	2.790	2.789
2	65.00	22.65	4.03	2.781	
3	67.60	20.96	3.74	2.779	
4	58.80	26.66	4.74	2.783	
5	69.80	19.54	3.47	2.785	
				Av. 2.783	

Values of Th and P vary because of the variable water content. In all cases, the ratio ThO₂/P₂O₅ is, however, constant within the experimental error and is in good agreement with the theoretical value. Hence the composition is fixed at Th₃(PO₄)₄.xH₂O.

1. Berzelius, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1829, 16, 385.
2. Berzelius and Cleve, *Bull. soc. Chim.*, 1874, ii, 21, 115.
3. Castel, *Compt. rend.*, 1939, 208, 519.
4. Cleve, *Kung. Svenska vet. Handl.*, 1874, ii, 6, 20.
5. Sollmann and Brown, *Am. J. Physiol.*, 1907, 18, 427.
6. Volck, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1894, 6, 161.

Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton thermobalance of 1 mg. sensitivity with a heating rate of 6°/min. A typical %weight loss curve is shown in Fig. 1 which shows gradual loss of water upto 250°, followed by a very rapid loss of almost all the water in the region 250°-350°, finally dehydrating completely at about 800°. There is no stepwise decomposition corresponding to hydrate of any fixed composition.

A typical D. T. A. curve, also shown in Fig. 1, shows a similar endothermic peak with a maximum corresponding to the T.G. curve.

FIG. 1. Dehydration curves of thorium orthophosphate.

(A) TGA, ● (B) DTA.

The results lead to the conclusion that thorium orthophosphate, as prepared by the wet methods, is a white gel, containing varying amounts of water and that no compound of the tetrahydrate composition is formed even as an intermediate. The amount of water varies not only with the method or batch of preparation, but also with conditions of storage.